

ENHANCING THE ROLE OF CORPORATIONS IN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT THROUGH IMPLEMENTATION OF ESG PRINCIPLES

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Abstract ESG stands for Environmental, Social and Governance and it is a set of criteria that investors and organizations use to evaluate a company's impact on society and the environment, as well as its overall management practices. In recent years, the importance of ESG has increased in assessing the long-term sustainability of a company, investor confidence and engagement, and companies that prioritize ESG initiatives in developing better relationships with their stakeholders, including employees, customers, suppliers, and the local community.

Keywords: SDG- Sustainable Development Goals, ESG, CSR, TBL, SSE.

After the adoption of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), a number of considerations emerged regarding the role of corporations in achieving the goals set in it. Because these goals encompass environmental sustainability, social and economic growth. Corporations have specific responsibilities in this regard. In particular, corporate social responsibility (CSR)

concern about the responsibility of the corporation in conducting business, compliance with the moral norms of the society, health and safety of people, human rights, environmental protection

and shows respect for society.

In turn, ESG (environmental, social and governance) is a comprehensive system that evaluates the general indicators of the company's sustainable development, including environmental, social and governance aspects. According to most studies, the term ESG appeared in the early 2000s. However, the term has been debated over the years by various stakeholders including scientists, investors and

corporations. In particular, the concept of socially responsible investing (SRI) appeared in the 1960s and 1970s and aims to take into account social and environmental factors when making investment decisions. Over time, it has evolved into a broader ESG concept that encompasses not only environmental and social factors, but also governance aspects.

Freer Spreckley was the first to use the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) triple bottom line in his work on social auditing in 1981. It suggested that businesses monitor and report on financial performance, social welfare and environmental responsibility. However, it was John Elkington who popularized the term "triple bottom line" in his 1997 book "Fork Cannibals." encourages to try to maintain and maximize profit.

The Triple Bottom Line (TBL) is a framework that expands the traditional approach to business performance evaluation by including social and environmental factors in addition to financial aspects. The TBL includes three "bottom lines" that a company must consider: people, planet, and profit. The ESG index was first launched in 2001 as a series of FTSE4Good indices and started as a measure to focus on social, ethical and environmental (SSE) issues for UK pension funds. Environmental management criteria, human rights criteria and supply chain labor requirements were established over several years in 2002, 2003 and 2005 respectively. Here are some key aspects of how ESG can contribute to development:

Environmental sustainability: ESG focuses on environmental factors such as climate change, resource conservation, pollution and biodiversity. By integrating environmental issues into development strategies, ESG can help promote sustainable practices, reduce environmental impacts, and mitigate climate risks. This leads to the preservation of natural resources and ecosystems for future generations. **Social responsibility:** The "S" in ESG refers to social factors, including labor rights, human rights, community participation, diversity and inclusion, and employee well-being.

Incorporating social considerations into development efforts ensures that businesses and organizations operate ethically, respect human rights, provide fair

working conditions, and contribute positively to local communities. It helps to improve social equity, inclusion and quality of life.

Corporate Governance: The "G" in ESG represents governance factors such as transparency, accountability, board diversity and shareholder rights. Good governance practices help create a stable and well-functioning business environment, increase investor confidence, and reduce the risk of corruption and fraud. By promoting effective governance structures, ESG contributes to the long-term stability and sustainability of organizations and economies. **Risk management:** ESG factors provide a comprehensive framework for risk assessment and management. By considering environmental, social and governance risks, businesses and investors can identify and mitigate potential vulnerabilities. This helps prevent negative impacts such as financial losses, reputational damage and legal problems, thereby ensuring more sustainable development. **Investment and financial decisions:** The introduction of ESG into company operations is becoming increasingly important for investors and financial institutions. By integrating ESG criteria into investment decisions, capital can be directed to companies and projects that comply with sustainable and responsible practices. It encourages the development of environmentally friendly technologies, social impact initiatives and well-run businesses.

In recent years, a lot of attention has been paid to the implementation of ESG principles in Uzbekistan. Implementing ESG (Environmental, Social and Governance) principles can pose several challenges for companies, regardless of their size or industry. While the benefits of ESG integration are significant, below are some common challenges that companies may face during the implementation process:

- One of the main problems in the field of ESG is the lack of understanding of ESG principles among company management and employees. Without a clear

understanding of the importance of ESG, companies may struggle to prioritize and allocate resources to address sustainability and social issues.

- Resource constraints: Integrating ESG practices often requires investments in technology, skills development and infrastructure. For smaller companies or those facing financial difficulties, it can be difficult to allocate the necessary resources to implement ESG initiatives.

- Data Collection and Reporting: Collecting relevant and accurate data for ESG reporting can be a complex and time-consuming process. Companies may struggle to establish robust data collection mechanisms and track progress on various ESG indicators.

- Short-term and long-term plan: ESG initiatives usually have long-term benefits, but some companies prioritize short-term financial gains over sustainable practices. Balancing short-term financial goals with long-term sustainability goals can be a challenge for companies.

Lack of standardization and metrics: The lack of standardized ESG metrics and reporting systems can make it difficult for companies to implement ESG principles in their operations.

Resistance to change: Implementing ESG often requires changes in company culture and operations. Resistance to change from internal stakeholders accustomed to traditional practices can hinder success in adopting sustainable and responsible practices. Stakeholder Engagement: Effectively engaging stakeholders, including employees, investors, customers and local communities, is critical to successful ESG implementation. Companies can have difficulty understanding and addressing the different interests and concerns of different stakeholders.

Summary

While implementing ESG principles can present challenges, companies that proactively address these issues reap many benefits, including improved brand reputation, increased investor confidence, increased operational efficiency, and

stronger social and environmental impact. can show. Embracing ESG is not only a corporate responsibility, but a strategic imperative for companies seeking to build a sustainable future. It is also necessary to promote a code of social responsibility, develop corporate governance standards, and at the same time strengthen control over the implementation of these policies and procedures with an emphasis on transparency.

The implementation of ESG principles in the company's activities is a necessity for success in the market. ESG is not just about doing good, but should be seen as an important strategy for long-term growth, sustainability and success. As companies take a holistic approach to ESG, we can become not just profit-seekers, but agents of positive change, contributing to a brighter and more sustainable future for all.

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